

Evaluation of the Frequency of Infertility in Males among Different Age Groups in Lahore.

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Abstract:

Objective: Analyzing the frequency of infertility among the males of different age groups in Lahore.

Design of Study: Descriptive case study.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in the Urology department of Mayo hospital Lahore in a period of 6 months from July 2018 to December 2018.

Materials and Methods: Individuals in different age groups were selected randomly and then classified into three age groups. Patients with age between 20-30 years were classified as group-1, those with age between 20-30 years were kept in group-2 and patients having age greater than 40 years were kept in group-3. Only those patients were selected who were willing to take part in this research. Informed consent was taken from each individual. Patients were asked to provide the semen sample which was then analyzed using light microscopy. Each sample was carefully sent to a reliable lab for semen analysis. The reports were then analyzed for sperm motility, morphology, contamination with microbes and presence of any kind of debris.

Results: Aberrant semen report was surprisingly found in people of young age about 58% compare to people in group 2 and 3 having anomalous reports of 52% and 60%. Abnormal motility and morphology was highest in people above 40 years of age. According to the study a higher risk of aberration is seen in young age group. Vitiate foods, climate changes, improper nutrition and change of life style are the main reasons behind this increasing abnormality.

Conclusion: The increasing abnormal reports is an alarming condition that is causing increased infertility in young generation and a proper solution must be found out to prevent the infertility in coming generations.

Key Words: Infertility, young generation, aberrant semen, incidence.

Introduction: Valuable information regarding semen morphology and motility is gained by semen analysis an older method for checking the semen report. However, due to varying parameters and partly because difference in earlier and new investigation and different methods adopted by the

laboratory technicians, the performance of evaluation in this way is helpful in guessing the performance of reproduction in an assisted reproductive setting. Failure rate of approximately 15% is seen in case of first pregnancy and is considered in this category if they are unable to have a pregnancy after one year of intercourse. All over the world infertility among the males is 20-30 reaching to 48.5 billion in total and the incidence of infertility in Pakistan is 21.9%.

Materials and Methods: This study was carried out in the Urology department of Mayo hospital Lahore in a period of 6 months from July 2018 to December 2018. A total of 516 patients were selected who were willing to take part in this research and were keen to find out the cause of infertility. Individuals in different age groups were selected randomly and then classified into three age groups. Patients with age between 20-30 years were classified as group-1, those with age between 20-30 years were kept in group-2 and patients having age greater than 40 years were kept in group-3. Only those patients were selected who were willing to take part in this research. Informed consent was taken from each individual. Patients were asked to provide the semen sample which was then analyzed using light microscopy. Each sample was carefully sent to a reliable lab for semen analysis. Samples were sent on priority basis to save the samples from being wasted due to contamination, temperature, PH and dehydration. The reports were then analyzed for sperm motility, morphology, contamination with microbes and presence of any kind of debris. After result analysis the result was finalized. Recording after the analysis of data was done according to WHO criteria except morphology 4%. People with age less than 20 years were not included in the study. SPSS version 20 was used to data analysis.

Results: Aberrant semen report was surprisingly found in people of young age about 58% compare to people in group 2 and 3 having anomalous reports of 52% and 60%. Abnormal motility and

morphology was highest in people above 40 years of age. According to the study a higher risk of aberration is seen in young age group. Vitiate foods, climate changes, improper nutrition and change of life style are the main reasons behind this increasing abnormality.

Discussion: 48% flow rate is shown by the male division between the ages of 31-40 years. Only 10% of the infertile patients above the age of 40 years visit the infertility clinic as shown by Merino and Carranza-Lira. Semen reports have been analyzed and compared between the group 1, 2 and in this study. It have become evident that the reports become abnormal with the increasing age and there is a massive difference in all the three age groups. This difference may be because young individuals are more aware about the issues and ready to face the problem without hesitation and partly because of vitiate foods, climate changes, improper nutrition and change of life style. It was seen that motility along with morphology if considered together have no significant difference

in different age groups 1, 2, and 3 (17%), (16%) and (18%) respectively. With this mandatory situation a study carried out by Swan SH 2006, by Carlsen E. et al 1992 and Homan et al 2007 showed that in last fifty years quality of semen has reduced. Significant reduction in sperm motility in people of old age have been shown by Nieschlag et al in a study where as in this research little reduction in sperm motility with increasing age has been seen with any considerable difference among the age groups (1-8%, 2-8% and 3-9%).

Conclusion: Abnormal morphology and motility is the main concern in all the three age groups in this study. Young adults are at a higher risk of having abnormal semen and this is because of the vitiate foods, climate changes, improper nutrition and change of life style. The increasing abnormal reports is an alarming condition that is causing increased infertility in young generation and a proper solution must be found out to prevent the infertility in coming generations

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